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**CHANGES IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN MUNICIPAL CORPORATIONS
OF THANE DISTRICT ON THE BASIS OF
EDUCATIONAL INDICATORS**

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Abstract:

Thane district have huge urban area including six Municipal Corporations like Thane, Navi Mumbai, Kalyan-Dombivali, Bhivandi-Nijampur, Ulhasnagar and Mira-Bhainder. All MNCs are attached with each other by railway line. With urban resources MNCs have to face their own educational challenges. U-DISE data of urban area is showing large amount of Out of School Children and shifting of children Marathi medium to English medium and privet schools. In order to address the above challenges, it is necessary to discuss the U-DISE data of Urban area on the basis of Educational Indicators like Access, Teachers and Outcome Indicators.

This section focuses on changes of elementary schools in Municipal Corporations of Thane district within 2007-08 to 2012-13. U-DISE data of MNCs in Thane District within said period is used for study.

Keywords: *U-DISE- Unified -District Information System for Education, Educational Indicators, GER- Gross Completion Ratio, NER- Net Enrolment Ratio, PTR-Pupil Teacher Ratio, Dropout, retention and transition rates, Gender Gap, Enrolment, Ratios, , RTE- Right to Education.*

Introduction :

District have availability of DISE data from 2002-03 and it has been strengthening districts Educational Management Information System (EMIS). This system is now known as U-DISE including data of first to twelveth class. This is used for school education statistics and annual work plan budgeting of Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan.

This data is having all information of Schools ,Teachers ,Enrolment and infrastructure available in schools of first to twelveth classes. Using this data of schools in MNCs, shown the status and changes of Govt. schools in this paper.

• Changes of elementary Schools (Managementwise) in Muncipal areas in Thane district

S . N .	Schools By Management	Stages in Schools						Progress incurred in 6 years in %	
		Primary (1 to 4)			Secondary (5 to 7)			Pri	Up. Pri.
		2007-08	2012-13	Progre ss	2007-08	2012-13	Progre ss		
1	Govt.	89	56	-33	320	356	36	-37.0	11.2
2	Granted	133	118	-15	207	222	15	-11.2	7.24
3	Non Granted	141	109	-32	378	546	168	-22.6	44.4
Total		363	283	-80	905	1124	219	-22.0	24.1

No. of schools at primary level are decreasing in all type of management but at upper primary level it is increasing at all stages. It is because most of the primary schools are upgraded in to upper primary stage.

At primary level decreasing number of Govt. schools are shown highest in Navi Mumbai (80.9%) and Thane (64.1%) MNC. In aided Schools ,it is decreasing highly in Kalyan (60%) and Thane (40%) MNC. In unaided schools ,it is decreasing highly in Thane (52.8%)and Kalyan (37.3%) MNC.It means Most of the schools are upgraded from primary to upper primary in Thane MNC.

At upper primary stage highest govt. schools are increased in Navi Mumbai(61%) MNC. In aided schools ,it is increasing highly in Navi Mumbai (31.3%) MNC. In unaided schools ,it is increasing highly in Thane (111.3%)and Navi Mumbai (61.8%) MNC.

The ratio of primary schools is showing decreasing trend but showing increasing at upper primary level. Govt. primary schools are decreasing but unaided upper primary schools are increasing in MNC area in Thane district.

It is more essential to pay attention towards Govt. schools to improve quality of education in MNC schools.

- Changes of elementary Schools (Mediumwise)in Govt.schools- in Muncipal areas of Thane district

S.N	Medium of Schools	2007-08	2012-13	Progress	Progress in %
1	Marathi	276	296	20	7.2

2	English	7	1	-6	-85.7
3	Hindi	37	42	5	13.5
4	Urdu	66	91	25	37.8
5	Gujrati	18	14	-4	-22.2
Total		404	444	40	9.9

Govt. Urdu medium schools are increased (37.80%) highly in MNC area. It is showing highly increasing in Bhivandi (86.6%) MNC and decreasing in Thane (11.7%) MNC. No. of Govt. English medium schools are decreasing (85.7%) speedily. Decreasing ratio of Govt. English medium schools is highest in Kalyan (100%) MNC and Thane (75%) MNC. Most of the children are enrolled in Private English medium schools.

No. of Govt. Marathi (7.2%) and Hindi (13.5%) medium schools are increasing slightly. But Govt. Marathi schools are decreasing slightly in Thane & Ulhasnagar MNC. It is highly needed to improve quality of Govt. English medium schools in MNC of Thane district.

- Changes of Enrolment of children in elementary Schools in Municipal areas of Thane district

	School Management	Effect on Enrolment within 2007-08 to 2012-13					
		2007-08		2012-13		Difference	
		Pri.	Up.Pri.	Pri.	Up.Pri.	Pri.	Up.Pri.
1	Govt.	110241 (22%)	35672 (14%)	95337 (17%)	39183 (13%)	-14904	3511
2	Aided	174906 (35%)	115276 (47%)	146624 (27%)	112037 (39%)	-28282	-3239
3	Un Aided	219633 (43%)	96546 (39%)	303304 (56%)	139857 (48%)	83671	43311
Total		504780	247494	545265	291077	40485	43583

Teachers in Govt. (MNC) Schools	2007 - 08			2012 - 13		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
Teachers	1122 (30%)	2670 (70%)	3792	1122 (31%)	2493 (69%)	3615

No special changes are seen in last 6 years in teacher ratio. At elementary level 69% female teachers and 31% Male teachers are working working in MNCs of Thane district which is quite better but more difference in working numbers of male and female teachers. Chart is showing no. of teachers are decreased slightly from 2007-08

CONCLUSION:

U-DISE data is showing trends in last six years in Schools of Municipal Corporations. Enrolment of Govt. and Aided Marathi medium schools is decreasing day by day. Most of the children and their parents wants to learn in English medium schools. There are a huse question mark showing on quality of Municipal schools.It is essential to give priority to improve the status of Municipal schools. Infrastructure of these schools should be improved. Appointment of essential teachers, enrollment of Out of school children ,Teaching process of teachers ,education of girls, mimority children, education of Children with special children, SC and ST children, Availability of educational Aids ;these are the most challenges in education of Municipal schools in Thane district. As per RTE mandate drop out rate and, Retention rate of children, NER, GER, PTR, Gender gap in enrollment should be control by local authority. MNC management should implement quality improvement programmes in Municipal area immediately.

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